

**ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF MONITORING THE LANDS OF RURAL
SETTLEMENTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

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Annotation. The importance of this work is due to the fact that the organization of land monitoring as an integrated system for monitoring the state of the land fund, assessing and forecasting its changes is a global task of the administration in the field of environmental protection and rational nature management in general. The purpose of the study is to identify current problems in the process of monitoring the state of land and to give recommendations for improving the procedures for performing these tasks.

Keywords: land monitoring, state of the land fund of the republic, principles of land monitoring, cadastral monitoring.

Introduction. The idea of global environmental monitoring of the natural environment and the term “monitoring” itself appeared in 1971 in connection with preparations for the Stockholm UN Conference on the Environment. For the first time, the term “monitoring” was introduced into science by Israel Yu.A., the organizer of the “Environment and Climate Monitoring” laboratory, opened at the Moscow Hydrometeorological Center and the Academy of Sciences [8]. At the first intergovernmental monitoring meeting (Nairobi, 1979), monitoring was used to refer to a system of repeated observations of one or more elements of the natural environment in space and time for specified purposes in accordance with a pre-prepared program [11].

Making effective management decisions on compliance with land legislation depends, first of all, on the availability of accurate scientific data on the quality of the land and its quantitative changes. Land monitoring is a source of such data.

Monitoring is, first of all, technical and information-analytical work associated with the use of technical means that monitor the state of land and changes in area characteristics, take soil samples, conduct engineering-geological and botanical studies of soils, analyze and measure their physical condition and the reasons for changes areas. We can say that monitoring is a means of both continuous, current and subsequent management [8].

The solution to these most important tasks in the overall land management system should be carried out in several steps:

- Collection of initial data on the state of the land fund using various modern methods and technical means of monitoring;
- Assess the quality of land plots, taking into account the interests of landowners and the most effective development for various functional purposes;
- Produce of technologies and regulations for making management decisions in the field of land management based on land monitoring databases.

State monitoring, depending on the purposes of monitoring and territorial coverage, can be: 1) Global land monitoring; 2) Republican monitoring of lands; 3) Regional land monitoring; 4) Local land monitoring [2].

At each territorial level, land monitoring may include the following subsystems for the corresponding categories of lands of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Monitoring of the lands of the Republic of Uzbekistan by categories of the land fund as of January 1, 2023

Figure 1 shows that the three largest categories of land in Uzbekistan today are: agricultural land (53%) the distribution of agricultural land in the republic is determined by natural and climatic factors; forest land (27%), as well as reserve land (14%). In total, these land categories cover more than 42 million hectares (94% of the country's territory) [1].

Depending on the purpose of monitoring, republican land monitoring can be divided into two types: monitoring of land use and land condition. Each object of republican land monitoring is described by a set of indicators that determine its condition and use [5].

The data obtained during the republican monitoring of lands are used in the preparation of the annual collection of the "Land Fund of the Republic of Uzbekistan".

In order to protect land resources and the environment in general, prevent land pollution, ensure their productivity, improve and introduce new technical means and technologies for monitoring land, as well as information support of the Ministry of

Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the state of land, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

1) timely identification of changes in the state of the land, assessment and forecasting of these changes, production of proposals to prevent negative impacts on the land;

2) provision of information to state departments on the state of the environment in terms of the state of land in order to implement the powers of these departments in the field of land relations, including production of the department for state land supervision.

3) providing local self-government departments with information on the state of the environment in terms of the state of the land in order to implement the powers of these departments in the field of land relations, including regional land control;

4) providing legal entities, private firm, citizens with information about the state of the environment in terms of the condition of land plots.

The goals and objectives of land monitoring are determined by the following principles of its management:

1. The principle of mutual compatibility and comparability of disparate data, which is based on the use of common classifiers, formats, data from the regulatory and technical base, a single state coordinate system and heights. This is the basic principle of land monitoring;

2. The principle of integration of methods and technologies of land monitoring;

3. The principle of reliability and accuracy is the correspondence of land monitoring data to the actual condition and use of the land fund;

4. The principle of completeness of monitoring information - the information must be complete and sufficient to solve specific tasks;

5. The principle of continuity of land monitoring;

6. The principle of visibility (using maps, atlases, diagrams);

7. The principle of accessibility (with the exception of information constituting a state or commercial secret);

8. The principle of economy and efficiency (application of methods, technologies, techniques for obtaining, systematization and storage of land monitoring data);
9. The principle of centralized management [1, 11].

Methodology. The method of obtaining information during the state monitoring of lands, which is carried out during the state monitoring of lands, is divided into 4 types, depending on the duration and frequency of action [2, 7]. (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Classification of land monitoring depending on the observation period

When preparing the final materials of the state land monitoring, it is indicated which types of surveys, observations and remote sensing were used. The necessary information for the implementation of state monitoring of land can be obtained in various ways.

Sources of information about the work carried out to study the state of the land are documents received by the state data fund, obtained as a result of land surveying during the calendar year, as well as data on the work carried out to study the state of the land, received from state and regional departments, local governments on request, from other official information resources [4].

In the course of the work, the analyzing negative processes and their causes are analyzed, maps of the dynamics of land use change are compiled. The revealed negative phenomena on the state of the soil cover and the use of land in the territory of

this area are the basis for the development of recommendations for the prevention and elimination of the consequences of negative processes.

The received materials and data of the state monitoring of lands are accumulated and stored in archives (databases) and databases of the automated information system of the state monitoring of lands [6].

The forecasts and recommendations presented in the reports to eliminate negative manifestations are mostly formal and cannot be applied to a specific situation for making managerial decisions. There are no mandatory administrative procedures that take into account the results of monitoring. The work done has not brought a perceptible effect either at the state or regional level.

Discussion. Having studied and analyzed the problems of state land monitoring in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Tashkent region, the following shortcomings of the existing system in this area can be noted:

1) As a result, the parameters are not defined, the absence of relevant regulatory legal acts in the field of monitoring the condition of land in rural settlements, as well as requirements for the content and structure of data obtained in the process of monitoring land at different levels (state, regional and district). Existing legal norms are usually limited to a list of specific activities, surveys and remote sensing that should be listed in relation to a specific category of land in a particular area. Taking into account the very importance of land as a natural resource, which is also a real estate object, and the fact that the data obtained during land monitoring are used in the implementation of the state land cadastre and land management, it is necessary to update the regulatory framework for land monitoring when developing plans of this kind as appropriate measures for land reclamation.

2) The absence of methodological and normative-technical documents regulating land monitoring and systematization of its data.

3) The lack of regulatory regulation of the mechanism of interaction of power structures, including the interaction of automated information systems. Based on the importance and significance of monitoring the lands of rural settlements for the

Republic of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to legislate the authority to regulate land monitoring in the relevant territory.

At the regional level, the right should be granted to establish in their acts the types, procedure for financing and objectives of land monitoring in their territories, a list of performers, frequency and timing of conducting, a list of studies related to the natural, climatic, socio-economic characteristics of the territory.

In order to form and improve the monitoring system of rural settlements in the Republic of Uzbekistan and improve the regulatory framework, it is advisable to adopt a target program "Development of state monitoring of rural settlements in the Republic of Uzbekistan", which would determine the main directions for the development of monitoring of rural settlements in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and in which, since the program activities will include:

1) Adoption of the necessary regulatory legal acts regulating the implementation of state monitoring of rural settlements' lands, interaction of state executive authorities delimiting their competence, and their adoption of regulatory legal acts legal acts regulating state monitoring of rural settlements' lands at the appropriate level;

2) Creation of a stable system of departments (and organizations) that allows continuous and systematic monitoring of rural settlements' lands;

3) Creation of a unified system of methodological and technical standards that ensure the compatibility of information obtained during land monitoring at various levels during monitoring of other types of natural resources;

4) Equipping the relevant institutions with the technical means necessary to perform the relevant work required in the process of land monitoring, the formation of data collections, the storage and processing of information and the maintenance of databases obtained in the process of land monitoring.

Conclusion. To ensure the consistency of the indicators used in land monitoring, as well as the harmonization and compatibility of various indicators in monitoring other types of natural resources, a monitoring system is proposed that includes three subsystems and a control unit (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Structural diagram of the land monitoring system

Cadastral monitoring organizes and conducts observations of changes in cadastral information, which include: change of ownership; change of owner; change in the shape and area of the land plot; change in the legal regime; change in cadastral and market value; change in permitted use. The functions of organizing and maintaining cadastral monitoring of rural settlements' lands should be assigned to the subdivisions of the Cadastral Agency.

Geodynamic monitoring organizes and conducts geodetic, geodynamic, seismological, geological and gravimetric observations.

The functions of organizing and managing geodynamic monitoring should be assigned to O'ZGASHKLITI, which has extensive experience in this field.

Modern IT technologies, methods of remote sensing of the Earth, GPS positioning, laser scanning allow collecting monitoring information in almost real time.

To store, process and transmit information about the state of the land, it is necessary to create a single monitoring scientific center.

The analysis of thematic and forecast maps and plans will allow not only to assess the condition of the land, but also to make effective decisions on territorial planning,

land management, calculate the scientifically based cadastral and market value of land, improve the taxation system and use the land fund of the Republic of Uzbekistan more efficiently and rationally.

For the development of state land monitoring, including the main sources of state land management systems, it is necessary to develop regulatory documents defining the purpose of land monitoring as a mandatory periodic measure to assess the condition and actual use of various territorial entities from another land plot to the country with the formation of databases of results, their storage and access to them. At the same time, doing these requirements is important for the formation and maintenance of cadastral systems, as well as many other land information systems, such as land assessment systems, monitoring systems for the condition and use of land. System of formation of state reports on land resources, land fund of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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